

LEVERAGING AI AND IOT FOR SUSTAINABLE WASTE MANAGEMENT: A FRAMEWORK FOR BANGLADESH

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Abstract

Bangladesh is currently experiencing severe waste management challenges due to rapid urbanization and population growth. In order to solve these issues in a sustainable way, the implementation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies can make process more reliable and efficient. This paper presents a tailored framework designed to leverage the coordination between AI and IoT within socio-economic and infrastructural boundary of Bangladesh. It aims to remodel the waste management practices. It encompasses several essential key components. AI-driven waste type detection and sorting methods offer precise and efficient methods to classify and handle various types for waste. IoT-enabled smart bin networks are capable of real-time monitoring and data collection. These technologies help municipalities to streamline their waste collection and disposal procedure. Community engagement is maintained through IoT-enabled communication channels that will boost public awareness and encourage citizen participation in waste management initiatives. This framework tries to offer actionable strategies by analysing existing waste management systems to address the key problems in waste management system. Successful implementation requires the integration of AI with existing infrastructure. Adopting this framework could revolutionize the nation's waste management ecosystem, promoting resilience, efficiency, and environmental sustainability. Using AI and IoT technologies in this sector, Bangladesh can progress towards achieving sustainable development goals while improving the quality of life for its citizens and preserving the environment for future generations.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence; IoT; Waste; Management; Bangladesh.

1. Introduction

Bangladesh is among fastest urbanizing countries situated in the southern part of Asia. Almost 38% of its total population resides in city areas[1]. This rapid urban expansion has significantly increased the generation, volume and complexity of waste, especially in major cities like Dhaka and Chattogram. The inflation in waste generation has had detrimental effects on urban life, environment and health of common people. As per SDG 11 give emphasis on the need to reduce per individual environmental effects of cities particularly focusing on the quality of air and management of municipal wastage of city areas by year 2030. Achieving this target is closely linked to other SDGs, like SDG 7, that focuses to ensure access to affordable, sustainable, and modern energy for all; where waste recycling may contribute to generate sustainable energy.

Waste can be defined as any material, substance, or object that has lost its primary value and is no longer being used; lost its purpose and needs to be disposed correctly. Waste can be generally categorized into hazardous and non-hazardous materials. Most of the industrial, electronic, and medical wastes are classified as hazardous. Non-hazardous waste includes municipal waste. Additionally, waste can be either solid or liquid, each requiring distinct disposal and management methods. Improper collection and treatment of both hazardous and non-hazardous waste can impose significant threats to the environment and public health.

According to the UN (1997), waste management involves the controlled management of waste materials from their source through the recovery stage to final dispose stage. Managing municipal solid waste in urban areas is a significant challenge due to its sheer volume and the complexities involved. Urban areas of Bangladesh produce about 25,000 tons of solid waste daily, with a per capita generation of 170 kilograms per year[2]. This figure has seen a dramatic increase from 6,500 tons per day in 1991 to 13,300 tons in 2005, doubling in just 15 years[3].

Bangladesh is developing rapidly with rising living standards. Its economic transition is marching toward a middle-income state. The amount of waste currently generated will inevitably grow. Various statics indicate that by 2025, the per capita daily urban solid waste generation will increase to 0.60 kg, up from 0.49 kg in 1995[1]. However, current waste management practices are marked by inefficiencies, including inadequate waste collection, costly disposal methods, limited land availability for final disposal, a lack of recycling policies, and insufficient public awareness about environmental issues.

To address these challenges, the integration of Artificial Intelligence and the Internet of Things into waste management processes offers a promising approach. AI can optimize waste collection routes, reducing fuel consumption and operational costs by analyzing real-time data and predicting waste generation patterns. IoT-enabled smart bins equipped with sensors can monitor waste levels and environmental conditions, triggering timely collections and preventing overflow. These technologies can also enhance sorting efficiency at recycling facilities by automating the identification and separation of recyclable materials. Additionally, AI can manage landfill operations more effectively, ensuring that waste is treated and disposed of in an environmentally responsible manner.

2. Methodology

This study uses qualitative research methods that includes key informant interviews (KIIs), integrated focus group discussions (FGDs), and qualitative observation menus. Officials from landfills made up the KII respondents who had sufficient job experience of at least 3 months, in addition to experts from civil society, academicians, researchers, and professionals in solid waste management (SWM) who are actively involved in SWM activities.

Two FGDs and three KIIs were done in total. Respondents were chosen for the FGDs based on their prior experiences of living close to the landfill. A balanced group of eight to ten respondents participated in each FGD, guaranteeing diversity in terms of age, gender, and occupation. To find the study participants, a purposive sampling technique was used, and interviews weren't done until informed consent was received. To understand the underlying meanings in the statements made by respondents, a thorough review and analysis of the data gathered using these techniques was conducted. In addition, the overall situation at the landfill site was evaluated using an observation checklist.

The general waste management framework, the leachate collection and treatment plant, the technique for measuring the deposited waste, the state and layout of the dumping platform, waste segregation and incineration procedures, safeguards for the landfill/collection area, and steps to reduce the exposure of nearby areas to hazards were among the main areas of assessment.

3. Waste Management in Cities

In urban areas, approximately 55% of solid waste remains uncollected[4]. The collection efficiency ranges from 37% to 77%[1]. This uncollected waste, generally plastics and polyethylene, often clogs drainage systems and pollutes water bodies, affecting water flow and contaminating surface and groundwater, soil, and air. This issue is especially critical in Dhaka, where surrounding water bodies have become so polluted that they pose a threat to human health and aquatic life. A major contributing factor to this problem is the lack of waste segregation, which leads to the accumulation of waste in cities. The 3R strategy (reduce, reuse, and recycle) is widely recognized as an effective waste management approach. By adopting this strategy, a significant number of recyclable materials, such as glass containers and plastic bottles, could be processed each year, creating substantial market value. Furthermore, the high organic content (70%) of the waste presents an opportunity to produce composting fertilizers, which could enhance food security as it will increase crop production by 25–30% and reduce the need for chemical fertilizers by 35–40%[1]. This approach could also generate jobs and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. However, in Bangladesh, recycling is primarily conducted by impoverished scavengers in the informal sector. Meanwhile the formal sector largely ignores the critical need for waste recycling, particularly in a densely populated and land-constrained country like Bangladesh.

In Bangladesh, just nine out of twelve city corporations have particular areas for dumping municipal waste. Due to the absence of proper landfill operation and management units, city corporations and municipalities use landfills as open-air dumpsites without any sanitary precautions. Although these sites were initially located away from human settlements, since 2010, communities have gradually expanded on open dumpsites, creating a risk of wastewater contamination nearby rivers.

Detailed information on some landfills is available in Table 1. Waste management responsibility falls on urban local bodies, including city corporations and paurashavas. With the approval of authorities, community organizations in larger cities collect wastage from households and local markets, while municipal staffs perform this task in smaller cities. The collected waste is deposited into designated containers provided by city corporations and paurashavas, and then city authority transports the waste to landfill sites for final disposal. People pay a nominal monthly fee to neighborhood organizations for collection services.

Figure 1: Location of Aminbazar and Matuail Landfill

Overall, the current condition of waste management in cities is inadequate. Khulna City Corporation collects 400 tons of solid waste daily, compared to the 550–600 tons generated by the city's one million residents [1]. The city authority is criticized for lacking the necessary logistics and for its negligence towards waste management. Gazipur, an important commercial city, generates roughly 2,500 tons of waste each every day[1], which is discarded in an open area alongside a national highway and thus waste to spill onto the road. The local authority has been unable to establish a designated landfill in the past eight years, highlighting the lack of systematic waste disposal. Such kind of severe conditions prevail in smaller cities.

The Aminbazar landfill is located in Savar upazila. It is about 24 kilometers northwest of Dhaka, started its operations in 2007 and covers 52 acres. It is operated by the Dhaka North City Corporation (DNCC). Like many landfills, it is situated near residential areas, water bodies, and agricultural land—approximately 500 meters away. It exposes these areas to various risks. Compared to the Aminbazar site, the Matuail landfill has a higher concentration of settlements and developed areas. The Aminbazar landfill, however, is located in a lower flood flow zone and is surrounded by multiple water bodies, agricultural fields, and a river. A multi-ring buffer

Table 1: Landfills and description

Name of city corporation	Landfill location	Landfill size	Proximity of population settlement	Establishment year	Number of dumped wastes so far (tons)	Presence of sanitary arrangements
Rajshahi City Corporation	City bypass	15.98 acres	Close to 500 meters	2004	1.5 million	No sanitary arrangement
Sylhet City Corporation	Beside Sylhet-Fenchuganj Road	7 acres	Within one kilometer	1995	1.8 million	No sanitary arrangement
Barishal City Corporation	-	-	Within 500 meters	2005	0.7 million	No sanitary arrangement
Khulna City Corporation	Rajbad	20 acres	-	1987	-	No sanitary arrangement
	Shaila	17 acres	-	2008	-	No sanitary arrangement
	Mathabhanga	25 acres	-	2015	-	No sanitary arrangement
Chattogram City Corporation	Halishahar	15 acres	-	1960s	6 million	No sanitary arrangement
	Arefin Nagar	19.5 acres	-	2010	3.5 million	No sanitary arrangement
Cumilla City Corporation	Jhakuni Para	10 acres	Within 500 meters	2008	0.5 million	No sanitary arrangement
DNCC	Aminbazar	52 acres	Within 500 meters	2007	-	Has sanitary arrangement
DSCC	Matuail	50 acres	Within 500 meters	1995	-	Has sanitary arrangement

zone analysis was performed to assess the distance from the landfills to environmental features using benchmarks of 500, 700, and 1000 meters, with longer distances indicating less pollution exposure. This analysis illustrates the spatial relationship between the landfills and nearby environmental features, including water bodies, farmland, and built-up areas, highlighting the potential for pollution from the landfills.

Table 2: Type of waste

Category	Definition	Components
Residential/ Household	This type of waste is generated in residential areas due to human and household daily activities. It is generated from family dwellings.	Food residues, paper, cardboard, plastic, textiles, glass, metals, wood, ashes, electronic items, batteries, oils, household hazardous wastes such as paints, solvents, cleaners, pesticides,
Commercial/ Institutional	These are the wastes generated from large institutional and/or commercial activities such as marketplaces, retail stores, restaurants, hotels, academic institutions, hospitals, government and private offices and buildings, etc.	Food residues, paper, cardboard, plastic, rubber, textiles, glass, metals, wood, heavy items, batteries, oils, hazardous wastes, etc.
Municipal service	These wastes are from sources like street cleaning, assemblies in parks, recreational activities, entertainment places, and relaxing places-beaches, etc.	Street cleaning, landscaping residual materials, tree trimmings and dry leaves, general wastes from parks, entertainment centres, beaches, and other relational areas.

4. AI and Waste management (Operational Background)

AI (Artificial Intelligence) has the potential to transform urban waste management by optimizing procedures, improving productivity, and encouraging sustainability. Here are some of the ways AI can be used in urban waste management:

- **Waste Sorting:** AI can automate waste sorting by analyzing images or using sensors to distinguish between different types of waste. Algorithms using machine learning can be trained to distinguish between materials like plastic, paper, glass, and metal, improving sorting effectiveness and recycling procedures.
- **Predictive Analytics:** AI algorithms can evaluate historical and real-time data to forecast waste generation trends. This enables municipalities to optimize waste collection routes and schedules by predicting waste accumulation locations and times, thereby improving resource allocation, reducing costs, and minimizing environmental impacts.
- **Smart Bins:** AI-enabled smart waste bins with sensors and compaction systems can monitor waste levels in real time. These bins can alert waste management teams when they are full, optimizing collection routes and preventing unnecessary trips.
- **Illegal Dumping Detection:** AI can aid in detecting and preventing illegal dumping by analyzing footage from surveillance cameras or other data sources. Image recognition technology can spot suspicious activities or unauthorized waste disposal, facilitating prompt intervention and enforcement.
- **Optimization of Recycling Processes:** AI can enhance recycling operations by improving the entire recycling process, from collection to processing and reuse. Machine learning algorithms can refine material sorting, identify the most efficient recycling methods, and explore opportunities for waste-to-energy conversion or other alternative approaches.
- **Resource Recovery:** AI can help identify valuable resources in the waste stream, such as metals or organic materials, for reuse or energy production. AI algorithms can analyze waste composition and suggest innovative resource recovery techniques, supporting a circular economy.

4.1 AI in Waste Sorting

AI plays several crucial roles in waste sorting, leveraging its capabilities in image recognition, machine learning, and automation. Here are the key roles of AI in waste sorting, along with some detailed examples:

- **Image Recognition:** AI algorithms can examine images or video footage of waste materials to identify different types based on their visual features. By training machine learning models with large collections of labelled waste images, AI can effectively categorize materials.

- **Material Identification:** AI can detect specific materials within waste streams, even when they are mixed or partially obscured. By analyzing attributes like colour, shape, texture, and density, AI can distinguish between various materials, facilitating better sorting and recycling.
- **Adaptive Learning:** AI can continuously improve its sorting accuracy by learning and adapting to new waste materials over time. Machine learning algorithms can be updated with new data to refine their models and enhance their recognition of emerging materials.
- **Contaminant Detection:** AI can identify and remove contaminants from recyclable materials, improving the quality and purity of recycled products. By analyzing waste composition with advanced algorithms, AI systems can separate unwanted substances that might interfere with recycling.
- **Optimization of Sorting Processes:** AI can enhance the efficiency of waste sorting by optimizing various processes. By analyzing historical and real-time data, AI algorithms can recommend the best sorting strategies, such as adjusting conveyor belt speeds, optimizing sensor setups, or reallocating sorting resources dynamically.
- **Quality Control:** AI can aid in quality control by detecting defects or impurities in recycled materials. By evaluating the characteristics of recycled products, AI algorithms ensure that only materials meeting the required standards are used.

4.2 AI in Predictive Analytics in the Context of Waste Management

AI plays a crucial role in predictive analytics for waste management, enabling authorities and waste management organizations to optimize their operations, reduce costs, and improve sustainability. Here are the key roles of AI in predictive analytics for waste management, along with detailed examples:

- **Waste Generation Forecasting:** AI algorithms can process historical waste generation data alongside real-time inputs like weather, population density, and special events to forecast future waste levels. By anticipating when and where waste will accumulate, waste management authorities can better plan collection routes, schedules, and resource use.
- **Route Optimization:** AI algorithms can enhance the efficiency of waste collection routes by incorporating waste generation forecasts, traffic conditions, and other relevant data. Analyzing both historical and real-time information, AI can identify the most efficient routes, reducing travel distance, time, and fuel usage. [5]
- **Bin Monitoring:** AI can track waste levels in smart bins and forecast when they will need emptying. By analyzing historical data and real-time sensor information, AI algorithms can estimate when bins will reach their capacity, allowing for optimized collection schedules and avoiding unnecessary trips.
- **Capacity Planning:** AI can aid in planning for the future capacity needs of waste management facilities and infrastructure. By analyzing historical data and waste generation forecasts, AI algorithms can predict future infrastructure requirements, such as additional recycling centers or waste-to-energy plants.

4.3 Smart Bin Systems

Normally, waste is stored in bins, and workers come in for their routine work and take the garbage regardless of how full the bins are. This procedure is not effective for a daily smart waste management system. To address the limitations, the entire system requires a smart bin that is intelligent enough to constantly monitor its own capacity and fill garbage. The smart bin system focuses on a few functions. Some of these include automatic waste monitoring, capacity and filled ratio monitoring, and so on. The smart bin system can be built using an MCU or MPU such as the ESP 8266 and any network connectivity, such as GSM. This intelligent bin can detect whether the bin is empty or full and send data to central control. Then this data is used to further analysis and system operation.

4.4 AI in Illegal Dumping Detection

AI plays crucial roles in detecting and addressing illegal dumping activities, leveraging its capabilities in image analysis, data processing, and pattern recognition. Here are the key roles of AI in illegal dumping detection, along with detailed examples:

- **Image Recognition:** AI algorithms can examine images or video footage from surveillance cameras or drones to detect illegal dumping activities. By training on labeled examples of known dumping sites, AI can effectively spot and report suspicious behaviors in real-time.

- **Sensor Data Analysis:** AI can analyze data from sensors like those monitoring air quality or waste composition to detect irregularities that might suggest illegal dumping. By comparing current data to established baselines, AI can spot unusual patterns or pollutants indicative of unauthorized waste disposal.
- **Pattern Recognition:** AI can identify patterns in waste disposal data, such as irregular collection routes or inconsistent waste generation, to uncover possible illegal dumping. By examining historical data and spotting deviations, AI can highlight suspicious activities for further examination.
- **Data Fusion and Integration:** AI can combine information from various sources, such as surveillance cameras, sensors, and public reports, to create a detailed view of illegal dumping activities. By merging and analyzing diverse datasets, AI can uncover hidden patterns and provide a comprehensive overview for better detection and prevention. [6]
- **Predictive Analytics:** AI can analyze historical data, environmental factors, and socioeconomic indicators to forecast potential future hotspots for illegal dumping. By evaluating various variables, AI helps authorities allocate resources and implement preventive measures proactively.

4.5 AI in Optimization of Recycling Process

AI plays a vital role in optimizing recycling processes, enabling waste management organizations and recycling facilities to improve efficiency, increase recycling rates, and enhance sustainability. Here are the key roles of AI in optimizing recycling processes, along with detailed examples:

- **Waste Sorting and Classification:** AI can analyze images or sensor data to effectively sort and classify various waste materials. Utilizing machine learning and computer vision, AI identifies and separates recyclable from non-recyclable materials, streamlining the recycling process.
- **Process Optimization:** AI enhances recycling processes by evaluating data on equipment performance, energy use, and material flow. By pinpointing bottlenecks and inefficiencies, AI suggests adjustments to improve operational efficiency and increase recycling throughput.
- **Predictive Maintenance:** AI predicts potential equipment failures or maintenance needs in recycling facilities by analyzing sensor data, past maintenance records, and operational metrics. By recognizing patterns and anomalies, AI forecasts maintenance requirements, helping to minimize downtime and maximize equipment availability.
- **Quality Control:** AI performs quality control by analyzing sensor data, visual inspection images, or material characteristics to ensure the purity and quality of recycled materials. It detects contaminants, impurities, or defects, enhancing the quality of recycled products and reducing processing issues.
- **Inventory Management and Demand Forecasting:** AI optimizes inventory management in recycling facilities by analyzing historical data, market trends, and demand forecasts. It considers factors like material availability, market demand, and price changes to recommend optimal inventory levels and improve supply chain operations.

4.6 AI in Resource Recovery

AI plays significant roles in resource recovery, aiding in the identification, extraction, and utilization of valuable resources from waste streams. Here are the key roles of AI in resource recovery, along with detailed examples:

- **Resource Identification:** AI algorithms can evaluate waste composition and sensor data to pinpoint valuable resources within waste streams. By applying machine learning and data analysis, AI can detect specific materials or components that are suitable for recovery and reuse.
- **Optimal Extraction Techniques:** AI can enhance resource extraction methods by analyzing data on waste properties, extraction technologies, and recovery rates. By assessing various factors, AI algorithms can recommend the most efficient and cost-effective methods for extracting different types of resources.
- **Process Optimization:** AI can improve resource recovery processes by examining operational data, energy use, and resource yields. By identifying inefficiencies and bottlenecks, AI can suggest adjustments to enhance the efficiency of resource recovery.

5. Integrated Waste Management Framework for Urban and Industrial Settings

Effective waste management is a critical challenge in rapidly urbanizing countries, particularly in regions like Bangladesh where population density and industrial activities are high. Traditional waste management systems often struggle to cope with the increasing volume and complexity of waste generated, leading to environmental degradation and public health concerns. To address these challenges, we propose an innovative waste management

framework that leverages Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies, ensuring efficient and sustainable waste management from household collection to final disposal.

5.1 Household Waste Collection and Initial Segregation

The foundation of this framework begins at the household level, where waste is segregated into different categories using tagged bags. Each type of waste—organic, recyclable, hazardous, etc.—is placed in distinct, color-coded bags. This practice not only simplifies the sorting process later but also encourages public participation in waste segregation. Research shows that source segregation can reduce the amount of mixed waste by up to 40%, significantly easing the burden on downstream processing facilities [7]

5.2 Smart Bins with Sensors and AI Integration

Once collected, these segregated bags are transported by municipal authorities to local collection points equipped with smart bins. These bins are outfitted with IoT sensors that continuously monitor fill levels and environmental conditions, such as temperature and humidity, which are critical for managing organic waste. The AI systems integrated into these smart bins predict the quantity of incoming waste based on historical data and real-time inputs, optimizing storage and reducing overflow incidents. Studies have shown that AI-driven predictive models can improve waste collection efficiency by 20-30%[7].

5.3 Centralized Command and Control

Data from the smart bins is transmitted to a central commanding unit, where it is analysed to create optimized waste collection schedules. This centralized system coordinates the deployment of collection trucks, ensuring that routes are planned based on real-time data to minimize fuel consumption and reduce greenhouse gas emissions. According to research, such AI-optimized routing can reduce transportation costs by up to 25%[5]. The central unit also manages the transfer of waste to secondary and tertiary points before it reaches the landfill, ensuring a streamlined and efficient waste flow throughout the system.

5.4 Industrial Waste Management

The framework also addresses industrial waste, which is often more complex and hazardous than municipal waste. Industries are required to either transfer their waste to designated landfills or establish on-site recycling plants. This dual approach ensures that industrial waste is either safely contained or repurposed, aligning with circular economy principles. In cases where recycling is conducted on-site, AI systems can optimize the process, enhancing material recovery rates by up to 15%[8].

Figure 2: Waste management and AI integration

5.5 Landfill Operations and Waste Treatment

At the landfill, the framework emphasizes the separation and treatment of biological and non-biological waste. Biological waste is directed to composting or biogas production facilities, while non-biological waste undergoes further sorting and processing. AI-driven sorting systems, supported by machine learning algorithms, significantly improve the accuracy and speed of waste classification, reducing human error and exposure to hazardous materials. Research indicates that AI-enhanced sorting can increase the purity of recyclable materials by up to 30% [9].

5.6 Automated Waste Processing and Recycling Distribution

The final stage of the framework involves the processing of waste with minimal human intervention. Machines handle the bulk of the recycling process, ensuring that materials are processed according to demand and market needs. AI systems then oversee the distribution of recycled products, matching supply with industry demand. This

automated approach not only improves the efficiency of recycling operations but also enhances the overall sustainability of the waste management system.

6. Discussion

The proposed AI and IoT waste management framework aims to transform waste practices in Bangladesh. By using smart bins with sensors and AI, it can predict waste patterns, optimize collection schedules, and cut costs. This system enhances efficiency, reduces overflow, and maintains urban cleanliness. Real-time data analytics will improve sorting and recycling, reduce landfill use, and streamline operations at treatment plants. Challenges include high initial costs, ensuring technology reliability, and achieving widespread adoption. Training and public awareness will be crucial for success. Overall, this framework offers a promising solution for modernizing waste management and fostering a cleaner, more sustainable future in Bangladesh.

7. Conclusion

The integration of AI and IoT into Bangladesh's waste management system presents a significant opportunity to address the challenges of rapid urbanization and inefficiency. By employing smart bins, AI-driven sorting, and real-time data analytics, this framework promises enhanced waste management, optimized collection processes, and improved recycling efforts. Adopting these technologies can lead to a more sustainable and effective waste management system, contributing to environmental preservation and better quality of life in urban areas.

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